

TRANSIENT THERMOELASTIC ANALYSIS OF CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITE BRAKE DISKS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a modeling analysis of transient thermoelastic behaviors occurring in Carbon/Carbon composite brake disks for an aircraft. A finite element code was developed which allowed an effective investigation of the transient thermoelastic analysis. Since the heat capacity of Carbon/Carbon composite is very large, the high temperature of the brake disk system was confined to only the narrow regions near friction surfaces. Therefore, Carbon/Carbon composite brake disk system has little dependency on the boundary conditions of the system. The composite brake disk system had the larger contact regions on friction surfaces than the isotropic metal brake disk system. In conclusions, Carbon/Carbon composite brake disks have excellent thermal characteristics as a brake friction material with the comparison of the isotropic metal brake disk system.

INTRODUCTION

Aircraft brake systems are usually composed of multiple disks, in which the wheel-driven rotors are sandwiched between stators held stationary by the brake structure. Braking action is achieved by pressing the disks with the use of hydraulic power, and heat is generated on the contacted surfaces of disks. Carbon/Carbon composite brake disks provide adequate structural, thermal and friction characteristics. For a normal landing, brake temperatures of 500°C are typical while temperatures up to 1300°C can be experienced during the short engagement time for a rejected take-off. Also, the use of Carbon/Carbon brake disks offered a 60% weight saving compared with steel[1]. For designing the

landing gear system of an aircraft, transient thermoelastic behaviors of Carbon/Carbon composite brake disks should be analyzed to understand thermoelastic behaviors that are subjected to considerable thermal loading. Zagrodzki[2] proposed a coupled thermoelastic scheme in the thermoelastic analysis of a steel multidisk brake. The finite difference method was used to solve the unsteady heat conduction problem while the finite element method was used to solve the elastic problem. However, the nodes of the finite difference method were not coincident with those of the finite element method. In such a coupled thermoelastic analysis, the use of the finite element method for heat transfer analysis is required because node point temperatures are needed for thermal stress analysis. Finite element formulations are adopted for both elastic and heat problems. Also, the fully implicit transient scheme is implemented. Advantage of using this finite element code for a problem coupled with heat and elastic phenomena is that the efficiency of the calculation is increased because the same node point variables of the same mesh layout are used in both heat and elastic analysis. The present work is based on the coupled theory that stresses and temperature fields are mutually influenced.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

In thermally orthotropic materials, the heat equation can be written as follow

$$(k_{lm}T_{,m})_{,l} + Q = \rho c \dot{T} \quad l, m = 1, 2, 3 \quad (1)$$

Using the Galerkin's method, the finite element formulation of transient heat Equation(1) is performed as follows

$$\int_V N_i \rho c N_j dV \dot{T}_j + \int_V N_{i,l} k_{lm} N_{j,m} dV T_j + \oint_{A_1} N_i h N_j dA T_j \quad (2)$$

$$= \int_V N_i N_j dV Q_j + \oint_{A_1} N_i h T_\infty dA - \oint_{A_2} N_i q_n^* dA$$

Equation(2) can be written in matrix form as

$$[C_T]\{\dot{T}\} + ([K_T] + [H_T])\{T\} = \{R_Q\} + \{R_\infty\} - \{R_{q_n^*}\} \quad (3)$$

Heat Equation(3) has the following form.

$$[C_T]\{\dot{T}\} + [K_H]\{T\} = \{R\} \quad (4)$$

In the present work, the direct integration method was selected. A direct integration scheme is based on the assumption that temperatures $\{T\}_t$ at time t and temperatures $\{T\}_{t+\Delta t}$ at time $t+\Delta t$ have the following relation

$$\{T\}_{t+\Delta t} = \{T\}_t + [(1-\beta)\{\dot{T}\}_t + \beta\{\dot{T}\}_{t+\Delta t}] \Delta t \quad (5)$$

In the present work, $\beta = 0.8$ was used which is an unconditionally stable scheme. An implicit method is developed from Equation(4) and Equation(5) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ([C_T] + \beta \Delta t [K_H])\{T\}_{t+\Delta t} \\
 & = ([C_T] - (1-\beta) \Delta t [K_H])\{T\}_t \\
 & \quad + (1-\beta) \Delta t \{R\}_t \\
 & \quad + \beta \Delta t \{R\}_{t+\Delta t}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

By use of Galerkin's method similar to the previous heat equation, the elastic finite element formulations are performed as follows

$$[K]\{U\} = \{F_f\} + \{F_{r_s}\} + \{F_T\} \tag{7}$$

MODEL OF MULTIPLE BRAKE DISKS

The schematic cross-section of an aircraft brake system in the $r - z$ plane is shown in Fig. 1. Only a half of the cross-section is to be shown because it is an axisymmetric model with respect to z -axis. By pressing the disks with hydraulic power, disks contact each other, and so heat is generated on the contacted friction surfaces.

The present model is a special case of the contact problem because it is non-isothermal and contact points appear simultaneously on many surfaces. In contact problems, the actual contact area is unknown in advance, therefore, any computer program for contact problem must include some form of iterations[3]. In each friction surface, a pair of contacted nodes are defined. One of the nodes is designated as the master node and the other as the slave node. Then continuity of the axial displacements at this interface is required for the each pair of contact nodes, however, discontinuity of the radial displacements can take place due to the slip at the interface. The following constraint conditions are needed for each pair of master and slave nodes at the interface.

$$u_{z \text{ at } M} = u_{z \text{ at } S} \quad \text{when } P > 0 \tag{8}$$

$$u_{z \text{ at } M} \neq u_{z \text{ at } S} \quad \text{otherwise} \tag{9}$$

By the continuity condition of the temperature field, nodal temperatures on the friction surfaces have the following constraint condition.

$$T_{at M} = T_{at S} \quad \text{when } P > 0 \tag{10}$$

By the relation $q^* = \mu Pr\omega$, heat which is called as brake capacity is generated on the contacted nodes of the friction surfaces.

$$q^* = \mu Pr\omega \quad \text{when } P > 0 \tag{11}$$

$$q^* = 0 \quad \text{otherwise} \tag{12}$$

On the friction surfaces, sliding in the circumferential direction take place. The radial component of the sliding velocity resulting from the deformations of the disks is considerably smaller than the circumferential component. An analogous relation holds between corresponding components of the frictional forces. Thus almost no frictional forces on the friction surfaces arise. In this sense the contact of the present model is frictionless [4].

Fig. 2 shows the finite element model with elastic boundary conditions. The A-B surface is pressed by the hydraulic pressure and the C-D surface of the left-end disk rests on the opposing plate. Axisymmetric 8 node isoparametric elements were used for the finite element analysis of the brake disks. There are 85 elements and 300 nodes per disk. The model contains 7 brake disks, and the whole system had 595 elements and 2100 nodes.

Fig. 3 shows the same finite element model with heat boundary conditions. The model has the prescribed convective boundary conditions (Cauchy condition).

METHOD OF SOLVING THE COUPLED THERMOELASTIC PROBLEM

At time t , solving Equation(6) yields the temperature distribution $\{T\}^k$ where the superscript k means the number of iteration steps. Using this $\{T\}^k$, the load vector due to thermal expansion $\{F_T\}^k$ in Equation(7) can be obtained. To solve the contact problem, Equation(7) is solved by an iteration method. Then new contact conditions and new stresses are computed from Equation(7) iteratively to meet the no-overlap condition and the equilibrium condition on the contact area. The fully implicit transient iterations are repeated at every time step to solve the equilibrium solution of the coupled thermoelastic equations until $\{T\}^k$ and $\{T\}^{k-1}$ are nearly the same. And then, new resultant thermal loading $\{R\}^k_t$, in Equation(6) can be constructed by the relation of brake capacity Equation(11). From these new $\{R\}^k_t$ and new equilibrium contact area, heat Equation(6) at time $t+\Delta t$ can be solved by carrying out the time marching. In this way, the history of thermoelastic state at any time was generated.

RESULTS

Carbon/Carbon composite brake disk is usually fabricated to show a transversely isotropic behavior in the $r - \theta$ plane to provide adequate structural, thermal and friction characteristics at the same time. However the material properties in the $r - z$ plane are inevitably orthotropic due to the laminated nature of the Carbon/Carbon brake disk. Therefore, many material properties for heat analysis as well as elastic analysis are needed in the thermoelastic analysis of Carbon/Carbon composite brake disks. The parameters for calculation are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters for calculation of the thermoelastic analysis

Properties	Symbol	Value [unit]
Elastic modulus in r-direction	E_r	50.2 [GPa]
Elastic modulus in z-direction	E_z	5.89 [GPa]
Shear modulus in r-z plane	G_{r_z}	2.46 [GPa]
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{r\theta}$	0.3

Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{r z}$	0.33
Thermal expansion coefficient in r-direction	α_r	0.31×10^{-6} [1/K]
Thermal expansion coefficient in z-direction	α_z	0.29×10^{-6} [1/K]
Thermal conductivity in r-direction	k_r	50 [W/(m K)]
Thermal conductivity in z-direction	k_z	10 [W/(m K)]
Density	ρ	1.80×10^3 [Kg/m ³]
Specific heat	c	1.42×10^3 [J/(Kg K)]
Convection coefficient	h	454.5 [W/(m ² K)]
Friction coefficient	μ	0.3

Fig. 4 shows the time history of $P_h(t)$ and $\omega(t)$ adopted for the present modeling analysis. The applied hydraulic pressure $P_h(t)$ was assumed to linearly grow up to 0.7 [MPa] till 0.4 sec and then, kept constant. The angular velocity $\omega(t)$ was assumed to linearly decay, finally become zero in 1.0 sec. The implicit transient time step $\Delta t = 0.0001$ sec was used in the calculations.

In order to obtain a clear view of the thermoelastic behaviors of the present brake disk system, the transient responses of the thermal state are shown in Fig. 5 for time $t = 0.2, 0.6$ and 1.0 sec respectively. The temperature distributions show high gradients near the narrow region of the friction surfaces. At $t = 0.6$ sec, the temperature distribution shows the maximum value during the entire application time span.

Fig. 6 shows the typical temperature isolines of the Carbon/Carbon composite brake disk system at $t = 1.0$ sec. Since the heat capacity ρc of Carbon/Carbon composite is very large, the thermal diffusivity is very small. Therefore, the high temperature of the brake disk system is confined to only the narrow regions near friction surfaces.

Fig. 7 shows the typical pressure distributions along the friction surface 1 for the time span $t = 0.1 \sim 1.0$ sec. The pressure distributions along the all friction surfaces 1~6 also have the same trend. The history of the pressures nearly matches to that of the applied braking pressure $P_h(t)$ and no abrupt change of pressure distribution occurs along the friction surfaces. The present analysis for Carbon/Carbon composite brake disks(orthotropic case) shows relatively uniform pressure distributions along the friction surfaces when compared with the results of the steel brake disk system(isotropic case) in Ref.[2]. Therefore, the contact areas of the present Carbon/Carbon composite brake disk system are very uniform and large when compared with the results of the steel brake disk system of Ref.[2]. The reason is that the contact area decreases as the stiffness in thickness direction E_z increase.

Due to the large contact area and the overall uniform pressure distributions along the friction surfaces in addition to the large heat capacity ρc , the Carbon/Carbon composite brake disks show better performance than the isotropic metal brake disk as a brake friction material.

CONCLUSIONS

A finite element code was developed that is adequate for the transient thermoelastic analysis of Carbon/Carbon composite brake disks for an aircraft. Since the heat capacity of Carbon/Carbon composite is very large, the thermal diffusion is very slow. Therefore, the high temperature of the brake disk system was confined only to the narrow regions near friction surfaces. It was concluded that Carbon/Carbon composite brake disk system, that has the small thermal diffusivity, had little dependency on the boundary conditions of the system.

The thermoelastic analysis of the Carbon/Carbon composite brake disk system showed that the composite brake disk system had the larger contact region along the friction surfaces than the isotropic metal brake disk system. Therefore, heat flows smoothly through the larger contact area. The contact area was dependent upon the value of E_z . It was verified that Carbon/Carbon composite brake disks have excellent thermal characteristics as a brake friction material when compared to the isotropic metal brake disks.

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Fig.1 Schematic cross section of A/C brake system Fig.2 Elastic finite element model of the system

Fig.3 Heat finite element model of the system

Fig.4 Time history of the inputs

Fig.5 Temperature distributions of the multidisk system

Fig.6 Temperature isolines of the system

Fig.7 Pressure distributions along the f.s 1